

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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EFFECTS OF ELECTIVE DELIVERY POLICY
ON CLINICAL AND COST OUTCOMES

A DOCTORAL PROJECT PROPOSAL

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

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DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

The United States is an increasingly attractive location for foreign mothers to deliver their babies. At one southern California medical center, many foreign mothers with late local third trimester prenatal care demanded early delivery (e.g., less than 39 weeks gestation). This led to increased numbers of infants admitted to the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU), reflecting potentially poor fetal outcomes and uncompensated costs for the facility. The hospital implemented a new elective delivery policy based on American Congress of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (ACOG) recommendations. During 2012, a team was formed to manage the processes, which included educational sessions and dissemination of the new policy to the medical and nursing staff. An evaluation that compared monthly numbers of scheduled early elective deliveries in 2011 to 2012 were compared to those from 2013 to 2014. Prior to the policy implementation, 277 elective delivery cases did not comply with ACOG recommendation standards (16% of all deliveries) compared to eight cases (0.4%) after policy implementation; 39 NICU admissions occurred prior to the implementation compared to three admissions afterwards. Uncompensated hospital costs dropped from \$254, 546 pre-policy to \$0 afterwards. These results indicate that the successful implementation of the policy promoted the safety and health of mothers and neonates, and decreased uncompensated costs for the hospital. Staff morale also increased due to pride in following ACOG recommendations and perceptions of enhanced neonatal safety.

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BACKGROUND

Problem Statement

The United States is an increasingly attractive location for foreign mothers to deliver their babies. As stated on the ABC News website (Dwyer, 2010), “the number of U.S. births to non-resident mothers rose 53 percent between 2000 and 2006, according to the most recent data from the National Center for Health Statistics. Total births rose 5 percent in the same period.” This phenomenon affects care at a local southwestern medical center where a majority of patients, nurses, and physicians are Chinese. At this center, following late prenatal care in the United States during their third trimester, foreign mothers often demand an early delivery as a result of their limited stay in the U.S. as well as cultural beliefs. Due to this demand for early elective deliveries, during 2012-2013, the medical center experienced an increase in infants of foreign mothers who were admitted to the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU). The need for NICU care indicated that babies were born prior to optimal birth dates, reflecting a major safety issue. In addition, although the foreign mothers demanded an early date of delivery, when their infants were admitted to NICU and they learned that elective early delivery is a poor decision, some refused to pay the NICU charges, leaving unreimbursed costs for the medical center.

Clinical Practice Guidelines

Current American Congress of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (ACOG) guidelines recommend that induced deliveries should only be scheduled when gestational age is equal to or greater than 39 weeks or when fetal lung maturity has been established (ACOG, 2009). This recommendation aims to inhibit infant complications relative to

early deliveries, which may result in NICU admissions. The recommended classifications for gestational age category from ACOG are as follows: Full term is between 39 and 40 6/7 weeks, late term is between 41 and 41 6/7 weeks, and post term falls at 42 weeks and beyond (2013). Another current ACOG recommendation is that cesarean delivery based on maternal request is not suggested prior to 39 weeks (ACOG, 2013). When implemented, these guidelines for elective delivery decrease neonatal risk associated with elective delivery (ACOG, 2009, 2013). Thus, key staff and administration at the medical center decided the ACOG guidelines should be followed to ensure optimal care, prevent NICU admissions, and thus, prevent non-payment for services. Furthermore, elective delivery is one of The Joint Commission (TJC) Prenatal Core Measurements (TJC, 2013).

An elective induction is one in which labor is initiated without a medical indication (Perry, Hockenberry, Lowdermilk, & Wilson, 2013). In my 20 years of experience, I have noted that Chinese women who request elective deliveries provide various reasons for their requests. These include wanting to have the baby on a specific day, living too far away from the hospital, transportation problems, feeling uncomfortable during the final few weeks of pregnancy, and fearing vaginal delivery. Usually, obstetricians schedule patients for an elective delivery based on their clinical judgment to avoid prolonged labor and to achieve safe delivery conditions for mothers and babies; however, some elective deliveries are proposed for non-medically related reasons (e.g., better income for delivering physicians, better time management, favorable exchange with the patient, reduced working at night, etc.).

Significance of the Problem

According to the March of Dimes (2011), a baby's brain at 35 weeks weighs only two-thirds of what it will weigh at 39 to 40 weeks. As a result of a more mature brain, a baby delivered after 39 weeks gestational age is less likely to have vision and hearing problems and is more likely to be able to stay awake and alert long enough to eat after birth.

In the United States, the labor induction rates doubled between 1990 and around 2010. In 2006, more than 22% (about 1 in 5) of pregnant women induced their labor (ACOG, 2009). Induction guidelines were revised by ACOG and published in 2009; these guidelines provide instructions regarding the most appropriate elective induction method to best enhance safety and quality practice. Risks associated with elective induction include increased rates of cesarean birth and neonatal morbidity (Clark et al., 2009).

According to National Vital Statistic Report (Martin et al., 2012), cesarean delivery rates increased from approximately 20.5% in 1996 to 33% in 2011. Of nearly four million births a year, one in three are delivered by cesarean delivery. Since 1996, cesarean delivery rates increased by more than 40% for all age groups, including for women younger than 20 years old (Hamilton, Martin, & Ventura, 2006). Elective cesarean is a significant factor in this increase. Physicians' approvals of maternal requests for cesarean sections without valid medical indications rose from 40% to 54% (Miesnik & Reale, 2007). Interestingly, female physicians may be less likely to perform elective cesarean deliveries compared to male physicians (Ghetti, Chan, & Guise, 2004). Potential risks of elective cesarean delivery include prolonged hospital stays for mothers,

a higher risk of infant respiratory problems, and increased chances of complications in subsequent pregnancies (ACOG, 2013).

Elective delivery prior to 39 weeks of gestation accounts for 10-15% of all deliveries, despite ACOG recommendations against this practice (Clark et al., 2010). According to the report from Gallagher, Bell, Waddell, Benoit, and Cote (2012), women are increasingly aware of the option to plan their deliveries. One out of four young pregnant women favored cesarean deliveries at maternal requests (28.6%); however, elective vaginal delivery and elective cesarean section prior to 39 weeks gestational age are inappropriate and are related to neonatal morbidity (Clark et al., 2009; Tita et al., 2009). Cesarean section rates for term infants (37 or more weeks of gestation) have risen by almost 50% in last decade (Menacker and Hamilton, 2010).

As a level II community hospital delivering around 4000 infants every year, the medical center where this project occurred focused on health improvement and healing through evidence-based practices. The hospital population consisted of 55% Chinese private-paid patients, with the other 45% of patients being Hispanics with MediCal insurance. In 2012, through a quality improvement project, the hospital developed elective delivery guidelines based upon the 2009 ACOG recommendation to improve maternal and infant outcomes. The recommended outcome was to eliminate elective deliveries prior to the gestational age of 39 weeks. In December 2012, the hospital disseminated the ACOG guideline to the hospital's community physicians through a directive that elective deliveries of women with gestations less than 39 weeks would not be supported.

There was a clear need to evaluate the effects of the implementation of the ACOG guidelines for elective delivery at the medical center. This information is needed to educate medical staff who continue to circumvent these guidelines and to share implementation information and outcomes with sister hospitals who have not yet fully implemented the ACOG policy.

Purpose Statement

The goal of this project was to examine the effect of the implementation of ACOG guidelines (ACOG, 2009) regarding elective deliveries on clinical (maternal and neonatal) and cost outcomes. The clinical outcomes evaluated included gestational ages of mothers having elective deliveries (after 39 weeks vs. prior to 39 weeks, with or without valid medical indications) and neonatal outcomes of babies according to mothers' gestational ages (admission to NICU, NICU admission diagnoses, and length of NICU stay). The cost outcome evaluated involved the amount of uncompensated costs for NICU hospitalizations due to elective pre-term delivery after implementation of the elective delivery guidelines. This project provided needed information regarding the impact of elective delivery policy on maternal and neonatal outcomes, staff compliance, and NICU fiscal outcomes.

Supporting Framework

As the guiding conceptual framework, the Iowa model of evidence-based practice was adapted to guide and evaluate the elective delivery practice changes (Titler et al., 2001). This framework illustrates the process of a practice change (Figure 1). The clinical problem (problem-focused trigger) was identified as early elective deliveries that resulted in increasing NICU admission rates, poor neonatal outcomes, increased cesarean

section rates, and reduced hospital revenues. In addition, the knowledge-focused triggers for change included the evidence-based guidelines from ACOG and March of Dimes. These organizations recommend that all elective deliveries should be scheduled after 39 weeks gestational age. With these triggers in mind, a team from the Maternal Child Health department was formed around November 2012. The team included the Department Chair of Obstetrics and Gynecology, medical director of obstetrics/gynecology services, NICU medical director, Risk Management department director, Medical Staff department director, and the Obstetric Nursing director. The team's charge was to assess and critique the current practices regarding elective deliveries at the hospital. They also were to create a new policy and procedures based on the knowledge triggers and clinical evidence in order to achieve a higher standard of care for patients, better health outcomes for newborns, and prevent uncompensated costs for NICU hospitalizations.

The new policy was then disseminated to the staff and physicians by various avenues. The elective delivery policy consisted of its purpose, ACOG and TJC examples of maternal or fetal conditions that may justify delivery prior to 39 weeks, definitions of medical diagnoses of gestational hypertension, criteria to confirm the definition of gestation, and scheduled processes of elective deliveries.

After the implementation of the elective delivery policy, the number of infants less than 39 weeks admitted to the NICU rate was expected to decrease as well as the NICU length of stay. The number of scheduled elective deliveries inductions and cesarean deliveries prior to 39 weeks was expected to be few, excepting women with

valid medical indications. The staff was empowered and allowed to refuse physician scheduling of deliveries prior to 39 weeks gestation.

Change Framework: Elective Delivery Prior to 39 Weeks

Figure 1. Change Framework: Elective Delivery Prior to 39 Weeks. Source is “The Iowa model of evidence-based practice to promote quality care” by Titler et al., 2001, *Critical Care Nursing Clinics of North America*, 13(4), p. 499.

INITIAL REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

An electronic database search (PubMed, CINAHL, Cochrane) was performed by using search terms that included elective delivery, guideline, outcomes, ethnicity, and financial impact. The review of literature is an on-going process and involves continuously modified search terms to ensure adequate coverage of the literature.

Search Results

Based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 19 research articles were selected and reviewed. The types of the articles selected ranged from a dissertation, research proposal, program evaluation, qualitative, and survey studies and literature reviews to that of high quality systematic reviews of controlled trials.

Thus, the quality of the articles selected varied and include qualitative survey studies, single crossover controlled trials, and a systematic review of randomized trials. The strength of the evidence reviewed ranges from Level I to Level VI in the hierarchy of evidence (Polit & Beck, 2008). While the majority of the evidence is currently of Level IV and Level VI status, a Level I and Level II article has also been included. Findings from the Level I systemic review by Issenberg et al. (2005) support the key concepts or variables identified in the other articles that are analyzed for this literature review and, therefore, findings are discussed within the context of the Issenberg et al. study.

Guidelines for Elective Delivery

ACOG recommended a new definition of the term “pregnancy” (2013). The recommended classifications are as follows: Early term at 37 to 38.6 weeks, full term at 39 to 40.6 weeks, late term at 41 to 41.6 weeks, and post term at 42 weeks and beyond

(2013). In the absence of clinically valid indications for an induction prior to 39 weeks, a fetal lung maturity test should be established. Nulliparous women with unfavorable cervixes will increase the risk of cesarean section two-fold (ACOG, 2009). Cesarean sections upon maternal request are not recommended prior to 39 weeks gestational age (ACOG, 2013).

Ethnicity Issues and Elective Delivery

Elective inductions and cesareans have differential risk profiles for women and neonates depending upon maternal ethnicity. African American and South Asian women's mean gestation length is 39 weeks and that of Caucasians is 40 weeks. African American and Asian women have a higher rate of primary, unscheduled, intra-partum cesarean deliveries compared to Caucasians (Edmond, Yehezkel, Liao, & Simas, 2013).

African American and South Asian infants delivered prior to 37 weeks have a lower risk of respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) along with a higher survival rate when compared to Caucasian infants (Balchin & Steer, 2007). Infants delivered after 39 weeks with respiratory problems do not improve among South Asian and African American populations (Balchin, Whittacker, Lamont, & Steer, 2008). For Caucasians, term pregnancy elective cesarean section without labor is the major cause of RDS. South Asians have had the lowest chances of transient tachypnea of the newborn (TTN) up to 38 weeks and RDS up to 40 weeks gestation (Balchin et al., 2008).

African American infants delivered 37 weeks and beyond have higher mortality rates than that of Caucasian infants due to meconium passage and respiratory morbidity. Among the Asian population, late gestation stillbirth infants occur one week earlier than Caucasian infants (Balchin & Steer, 2007). In addition, African American women are

more likely to experience cesarean sections for fetal distress compare to Caucasian women (Edmond et al., 2013). There is no evidence specific to Chinese babies and the outcomes addressed here.

Elective Cesarean Section

According to ACOG, the risk of respiratory morbidity, including TTN, RDS, and persistent pulmonary hypertension, is higher for elective cesarean delivery compared to vaginal delivery, when delivery occurs prior to 39 to 40 weeks gestational age (*OR* 2.6; 95% CI: 1.35-5.90; $p < .01$). In circumstances where risk indications are absent for the mother and infant for a cesarean section, scheduled vaginal deliveries are highly recommended for the safety of the mother and infant. Furthermore, the risks of placenta previa, placenta accrete, and gravid hysterectomy increase with each cesarean delivery (ACOG, 2013).

According to Miesnik and Reale (2007), 40 to 54% of physicians have allowed women to request cesarean delivery without medical indication. Alnaif and Beydoun found 71.7% of hospitals in the Commonwealth of Virginia allowed on-demand cesarean delivery (2012). Male physicians tend to agree to perform cesarean sections more often than female physicians (Ghetti et al., 2004). The association between the size of the hospital and provider characteristics and the practice of on-demand cesarean delivery has not been found to be significant. Labor and Delivery managers' perceptions of on-demand elective cesarean sections have little relationship with hospital characteristics (Alnaif & Beydoun, 2012).

Gallagher et al. (2012) surveyed young women in their first pregnancy and their attitudes toward cesarean delivery on maternal demand. They concluded that women

residing with parents ($p = .005$) and those with midwife as favorable caregiver ($p = .013$) were less likely to prefer cesarean sections. Cesarean section on maternal request ($p < .001$) was related to a woman's decision regarding cesarean section. Young women are discussing the topic of cesarean section on maternal request and may impact others' decisions regarding a more favorable delivery mode (2012).

Elective Induction vs. Hospital New Policy

Hospital policies discouraging elective labor will reduce induction and increase unplanned labor rates. In fact, 63% of women educated about labor induction based on ACOG recommendations decided not to have an elective induction (reference). In a systematic review evaluating the impact of elective induction policy implementation both maternal morbidity and the rate of neonatal intensive care unit admission decreased (Akinsipe, Villalobos, & Ridley, 2012).

Little et al. (2014) investigated the impact of the ACOG national elective delivery guideline on obstetric practice and perinatal morbidity in a single hospital. The five-year retrospective study found among all deliveries between 2006 and 2007, 6.5% of women delivered at 38.6 weeks and 8% women delivered after 39 weeks. Among deliveries between 2010 and 2011, more than 4.5% delivered at 38.6 weeks and more than 10% at greater than 39 weeks. No apparent change was seen in the NICU admission rate ($p=.11$).

Elective Delivery Outcomes

ACOG suggests nulliparous women should be counseled when planning to have an induction of labor because of the resultant two-fold increase in risk of cesarean section (ACOG, 2009). One factor to consider is cervical ripening, which will facilitate the process of cervical softening, thinning, and dilating. The status of the cervix can be

determined by the Bishop scoring system. If the Bishop score is 6 or less, the woman has an unfavorable cervix. Logistical reasons for induction include, risk of rapid labor, distance from hospital, gestational age criteria met, and a mature fetal lung test (2009). In a prospective, observational study (Clark et al., 2009), the cesarean delivery rate in induced women was highly affected by initial cervical dilation and parity. Women choosing an elective induction with unfavorable cervixes should be counseled regarding an increased likelihood of a cesarean section delivery (Clark et al., 2009).

Clark et al. (2009) has shown that among planned deliveries without medical indication, 17.8% infants were delivered between 37 and 38 weeks, and of those, 8% were admitted to a newborn special care unit for an average of 4.5 days, compared to 4.6% of infants delivered at 39 weeks or beyond. Others have also shown that elective delivery prior to 39 weeks increases chances of neonatal complications (Hoffmire, Chess, Saad, & Glantz, 2012; Lee & Alton, 2008; Tina, Landon, & Spong, 2009; Wilmink & Hukkelhoven, 2010). Deliveries between 37 and 38 weeks have a doubly increased risk of respiratory distress, oxygen use, continued positive airway pressure use, and composite respiratory morbidity (Ghartey & Coletta 2012). Elective vaginal, elective cesarean section, and non-elective cesarean section delivery dramatically increases the chances of NICU admission in comparison to infants delivered by experiencing the onset of labor. Elective delivery infants were more likely to be SGA or LGA compared to infants born by experiencing the onset of labor ($p < .001$) (Hoffmire et al., 2012).

According to Lee and Alton (2008), respiratory morbidity significantly increases for neonates delivered by cesarean without the onset of labor (35.5/1000 deliveries)

compared to neonates born by cesarean sections (12.2/1000; $p < .0001$) or vaginal delivery (5.3/1000, $p < .0001$) after the onset of labor.

Risks, including fevers, infections, pneumonia, and thromboembolic diseases in postpartum women also increase with cesarean deliveries. The risk of placental abruption and placenta previa increases after the first cesarean delivery and with each subsequent cesarean (Miesnik & Real, 2007).

Financial Impact

Following a review of literature, Petrou and Khansuggested (2013) report that planned cesarean sections may be less costly than planned normal spontaneous vaginal deliveries (NSVD)for a fetus with breech presentation (Canadian \$7,165 vs. US \$8,042). Furthermore, failed vaginal birth after cesarean section is the most expensive birth due to the expense from the operative resources and infant NICU admission costs. However, for low risk cases, cesarean sections cost more than NSVD. Trial of labor following a previous cesarean section is more cost-effective than an elective cesarean section. In a prior literature review, Miesnik and Real (2007) reported that a vaginal birth costs 24% less than cesarean deliveries.

METHODS

Intervention

During 2012, 40 obstetricians (35 males and 5 females), 8 anesthesiologists, and 70 labor and delivery staff were involved in the policy and practice change regarding elective delivery for this study. Team dynamics were carefully considered and opinions were sought from obstetricians, neonatologists, anesthesiologists, registered nurses, and other staff members prior to finalizing the policy. Only then was an official memorandum regarding mandatory implementation of elective delivery to be equal to or more than 39 weeks gestational age drafted by the team and signed by the hospital obstetrician and gynecologist Department Chairman and Medical Director. A physician champion volunteered to help educate the physicians and support the changes. Around November 2012, the memorandum and policy were emailed and faxed to the physicians and the policy was posted in the physician's dining room and lounge. Physicians were informed of the new Policy and Procedure in the monthly meeting of hospital obstetricians and gynecologists. The unit staff [unit secretary, obstetrician technician (OBT), and registered nurses (RNs)] who work in Labor and Delivery attended an in-service regarding the requirements for elective deliveries. This staff education included the elective delivery policy and valid indications that would allow patients to be scheduled for elective delivery prior to 39 weeks. An elective delivery schedule spread sheet and binder were created and placed in the nursing station.

A peer review system was created to oversee the compliance of the scheduling. After the policy change, the nursing director in the unit reviewed the schedule for elective delivery cases daily to confirm adherence to the elective delivery policy. Staff members referred scheduling decisions to the nursing director for any uncertain cases. If the

physician insisted on scheduling an early elective delivery without a valid reason, despite the unit Medical director's recommendation, the nursing director referred the case to the risk management director for arranging peer review. Unit staff feedback regarding the implementation of the new elective delivery policy was allowed anytime.

Evaluation

A retrospective data review was conducted at the medical center. This investigation included all women who delivered with an elective delivery over the four-year period between January 1, 2011 and December 31, 2014. Outcomes were monitored by comparing the 2011, 2012, 2013, and 2014 infant gestational ages of mothers having elective deliveries (39 or later weeks vs. prior to 39 weeks), NICU admission rates, and neonatal outcomes for elective deliveries prior to 39 weeks. Staff adherence to the policy was measured by comparing the monthly numbers of scheduled early elective deliveries in 2011 to 2012 versus 2013 to 2014. The NICU financial loss from elective deliveries was also one of the outcome measurements compared two years before and after the policy implementation.

Data, such as the total number of elective deliveries (including scheduled cesareans and inductions), the number of elective deliveries of prior to 39 weeks, admissions to NICU prior to 39 weeks gestational age, NICU admission diagnoses, length of NICU stay, as well as uncompensated costs for NICU hospitalizations due to elective pre-term delivery were available and obtained from department monthly reports kept in the Medical Staff Department as well as the Labor and Delivery log book and NICU admissions log book. Chart reviews were used to obtain the numbers of infants admitted to NICU (determined by diagnoses) and NICU lengths of stays. The

uncompensated costs for NICU were obtained from the accounting department. Data analysis consultation was sought to determine the correct statistical analyses of the available data.

Ethical Issues

The project proposal was submitted to CSUF IRB for review and approved. Prior to submission to the IRB, permission from the hospital quality improvement director was sought to use existing data for this project.

PROJECT RESULTS

This investigation compared numbers of total deliveries and inappropriate elective deliveries prior to 39 weeks gestation with resulting NICU admissions, and the length of stay of those infants for the years 2011 through 2014. Over this period, total deliveries per month ranged from 250 to 430. The mean monthly number of deliveries in 2011 was 284 compared to 374 in 2014. Regarding deliveries taking place during the period of study, a total of 16,451 deliveries were observed, with average of 343 deliveries per month (range: 247 – 423, SD = 47.7). A total of 450 inappropriate deliveries were observed, with distinctly difference distributions before and after policy implementation in December 2012. Prior to policy implementation, a total of 442 inappropriate deliveries were observed with an average of 18 cases per month (range: 5 – 38, SD =8.9), while after implementation only 8 inappropriate deliveries were observed with an average of 0.3 cases per month (range: 0 – 3, SD = 0.8).

Figure 2 displays total elective deliveries along with inappropriate early deliveries. In 2011, there were 165 inappropriate early elective deliveries, and 277 in 2012. Following implementation of the policy at the end of 2012, there were eight inappropriate elective deliveries in 2013. Inappropriate elective deliveries dropped to zero in 2014. The total elective deliveries prior to 39 weeks was 48 in the month of April 2012, and after implementing the elective delivery policy it decreased to two in the month of December 2014.

Figure 3 displays inappropriate elective deliveries prior to 39 weeks gestation with resulting NICU admissions. In 2011, there were 21 NICU admissions resulting from inappropriate early elective deliveries and 18 NICU admissions from inappropriate

early elective deliveries in 2012. Following implementation of the policy in late December 2012, there was only one NICU admission in 2013 resulting from an inappropriate early elective delivery. From November 2013 through 2014, there were no inappropriate early elective deliveries and thus no resulting 2014 NICU admissions. In Table 1, the total number of days spent in NICU for these infants were 101 days in 2011 (21 infants) and 114 days in 2012 (18 infants). In 2013, the total length of stay for the single inappropriate early elective delivery infant was eight days. The diagnosis for the infant admitted to NICU in 2013 was Intrauterine Growth Retardation (IUGR). The case was scheduled at 38⁶/₇ weeks for a scheduled repeat cesarean section with Apgar 9-9. The infant was admitted to NICU for eight days with antibiotic treatment.

In 2014, the hospital joined California Maternal Quality Care Collaborative (CMQCC) to improve childbirth outcomes in California. This played a factor in the success of the elective policy. The hospital has met the national target, which is less than 5% of inappropriate cases for elective delivery. Figure 4 shows results reported to CMQCC of elective deliveries prior to 39 weeks rate using The Joint Commission Algorithm. All deliveries were involved; the algorithm screens the total number of deliveries, excluding all data but deliveries between 37 weeks to 39 weeks. The reporting requirement from The Joint Commission for elective delivery is then used, which we have adopted as a new clinical care policy for elective delivery in 2012.

Figure 2. Percentage of total elective deliveries that were inappropriate. On December 12, 2012 the policy was created. A policy memorandum was sent to physicians. Staff training session was conducted, and then the policy was implemented.

Figure 3. Inappropriate cases of elective delivery less than 39 weeks and NICU admissions.

Period	Garfield
Sep - Nov 2014	3.3%
Jun - Aug 2014	3.6%
Mar - May 2014	0.6%
Dec 2013 - Feb 2014	2.9%
Sep - Nov 2013	1.1%

Figure 4. Elective delivery prior to 39 weeks rate reported from California Maternal Quality Care Collaborative (CMQCC).

Table 1

Inappropriate Early Delivery cases with NICU Admission, Diagnoses and Refusal to Pay Costs

Year	NICU admission	Refusal to pay cases	Total length of stay	Diagnoses	Refusal to pay
2011	13	1	102	Respiratory Distress Syndrome (RDS), Hyperbilirubinemia, Pneumonia, Sepsis, Transient Tachypnea of Newborn (TTN), Small then gestational Age (SGA)	\$209,054
2012	14	2	114	Respiratory Distress Syndrome (RDS), Sepsis, Hypoglycemia	\$45,492
2013	1	0	8	Intrauterine Growth Retardation (IUGR)	0
2014	0	0	0		0

DISCUSSION

A term pregnancy is considered the period three weeks before the expected due date and two weeks after (ACOG, 2013). Poor neonatal outcomes, especially respiratory morbidity, are associated with elective deliveries prior to 39 weeks (Alan et al., 2009). The ACOG recommendation underscores the importance that elective delivery of an infant should not occur prior to 39 weeks gestation (ACOG, 2013). In Chinese culture, choosing a specific date of delivery is considered good luck, and in a local southwestern medical center where the majority of patients, registered nurses, and physicians are Chinese, the practice of elective delivery prior to 39 weeks was common and did not follow ACOG recommendations. The increased patient demand for early elective delivery resulted in more infants requiring NICU care. Once parents learned that early elective delivery was not standard practice, they refused to pay for NICU care at the hospital or for the deposit required to transfer their infant to a higher level of care. This resulted in an increase in the hospital's financial burden.

Using ACOG recommendations for appropriate elective deliveries, we found foreign women who underwent an elective delivery absent of first trimester ultra sound documentation did not have an accurate expected date of delivery. The expected date of delivery was based on physicians' documentation in the prenatal records, which can be inaccurate for women traveling to the United States for delivery, and thus, beginning prenatal care late in the United States.

Beginning in December 15, 2012, processes described in The Iowa Model of Evidence-Based practice were put into effect to improve outcomes of elective deliveries. Unnecessary NICU admissions and increased uncompensated costs caused the hospital to

reevaluate its policies. A team, composed of multi-disciplinary members, including medical chair, neonatologist, perinatologist, hospital risk manager, and unit nursing director, was formed to promote the success of recommended changes. The medical director, neonatologist, risk management director, and nursing director were the key drivers of the change processes. The policy was finalized through important contributions from the key players.

The principal change was to provide the right tools and information to the right people. Initially, this involved increasing provider awareness of the new evidence-based elective delivery policy and how it supported improved maternal and neonatal care. The policy change required the adoption and integration of the new practice throughout the organization. An official memorandum regarding implementation of the new elective delivery policy was relayed to physicians by email, fax and posters; a physician change champion monitored physician behavior. The unit staff attended an in-service on the new policy for elective delivery during a regularly scheduled staff meeting. Staff members who missed the in-service were provided information through the unit charge nurses. The new policy was available in the schedule binder together with the schedule spreadsheet. The unit staff was responsible for the scheduling; whoever answered the phone would assist physicians by updating the elective delivery schedule on the schedule spreadsheet located in the nursing station.

Feedback on policy implementation success was shared with nursing and medical staff. The number of monthly elective deliveries, the reasons of elective deliveries prior to 39 weeks, and the number and reasons of NICU admissions were reported in the monthly OB/GYN meetings. These reports played a critical role for administration, staff

and physicians, and functioned as evaluation tools and as audit and feedback to staff providers (Jamtvedt et al., 2006). The almost immediate change in patient outcomes (e.g., numbers of appropriate vs. inappropriate deliveries) showed high compliance by providers with the new policy. A high compliance rate meant care was improved, and patients were safer under the hospital's care. Ultimately, it resulted in positive patient care outcomes and decreased hospital costs. Some limitations included staff's preference to maintain good relationships with physicians and delayed reports for noncompliant cases. Assigning the responsibility for the scheduling to a specific scheduler addressed this limitation and improved consistency in the scheduling of elective deliveries.

As change often evokes a sense of loss, reactions to change by individuals or professional groups can be negative and unpredictable. Even a few disaffected individuals can cause disruption (Scott et al., 2003). Employees presented various behavioral responses to the new policy and practice changes. Reactions encountered during the policy change of elective delivery found that a few physicians and staff were unhappy and created great challenge. Required change leads to variations in peoples' response to change (Bushy & Kamphuis, 1989). Consequently, variations also exist in rejection and acceptance of innovations, and, over time, behavioral responses tend to remain consistent. Of the few disaffected physicians and staff, the more time they had devoted their careers to the unit, the more they resisted the changes. Generally, those who were more mature and had limited formal education were more apprehensive regarding innovations and changes. These physicians and staff have practiced for a longer time, so it was more difficult for them to change their past practices and adapt to the new policies. These were often the physicians who gave the same diagnoses over and

over, scheduling cases prior to 39 weeks. Some staff members allowed the physicians to schedule in this manner without alerting a higher authority.

To assist those not making the required change, the unit medical director implemented a peer review system to oversee scheduling compliance. The nursing director in the unit reviewed the schedule for elective delivery cases to confirm adherence to the elective delivery policy. For any elective delivery scheduled by the nursing staff that was not compliant with the policy, the unit director provided one on one coaching and arranged in-service training for nursing staff as soon as possible. Because the consistency of the peer review system and individual coaching with staff was maintained, the practice changes were sustained.

Despite obstacles with those who lagged behind in change, the majority of the physicians and staff were early adopters. According to Rogers (1983), early adopters are well integrated into the local system. Considered opinion leaders, these individuals were sought out by their peers for advice and were considered opinion leaders within a system. These early adopter staff members presented a lot of support throughout the elective delivery policy change process. The early adopters reminded the physicians that patients who had not yet reached 39 weeks were not eligible for an elective delivery or requested clarification without hesitation from the unit director. To strengthen their influential position in the unit, the unit directors tried to limit the challenges the staff would encounter with older physicians and staff members. The directors encouraged direct open communication to clarify questions regarding the policy change. Staff educational meetings helped to clarify and reinforce the new policy.

Some elective cases prior to 39 weeks had appropriate reasons, but a number of infants were still admitted to the NICU. In some situations, physicians provided an incorrect expected date of confinement (EDC) that led to infant admittance to the NICU. For example, a case reported by the office clerk stated the patient EDC was 1/14/2013, but when the patient arrived at the unit, the due date on the prenatal record showed 1/21/2013. The patient insisted she was experiencing labor pain and other labor signs. The physician, after receiving the report from the unit registered nurse, decided to keep the patient and proceeded with a scheduled cesarean section. The case was considered because the patient was in labor. The baby was admitted to the NICU for 10 days for RDS.

There were discrepancies between Labor and Delivery's elective delivery record and CMQCC data center report. The CMQCC report displayed that the total inappropriate cases met the national target of less than 5% with a range of 0.6% to 3.6%. During the same period the unit records showed that inappropriate cases were 0%. Reviewers are not from the labor and delivery department, so mistakes may be made while doing chart review. Furthermore, nurses might have missed diagnoses in initial assessments. This is an area for improvement in record reporting.

Currently, the administration, medical director, medical chair and unit director are looking for strategies to complement the current policy adopted from ACOG to promote the best care for patients. In order to encourage and motivate international patients to pursue complete prenatal care, ultrasounds and blood tests, the hospital plans to work with a group of perinatologists to check on international patients; the total cash delivery charge will be increased \$300, but the hospital will return that amount to patients who

have received the recommended care in the United States from our perinatologists. This plan would ensure patients who plan to deliver in the hospital receive proper prenatal care. With proper care, early problems can be detected, and the hospital would be able to provide needed patient consultations and explain possible infant outcomes before the delivery. If there is a need to transfer to a higher level of care, then physicians will assist the patients with this transfer.

In addition to the strategies above, the hospital nursing director limited the scheduled elective time slots beginning February 2015. A total maximum of six elective cesarean sections and four elective inductions were allowed within a 24-hour period. This restriction will prevent excess requests that previously occurred on days considered by foreign born mothers to be particularly auspicious for an infant's birth.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

We found that the NICU admissions and inappropriate elective deliveries prior to 39 weeks gestation significantly declined after the implementation of a new policy based on ACOG's recommendations. The process of change was challenging, but the outcome has been very rewarding both because of the reduction in inappropriate early deliveries and resulting NICU admission and thus, improved outcomes in terms of healthier infants, but also because the staff appreciates working in a unit that is following recommended guidelines where they can provide excellent care to mothers and infants at the time of labor and delivery and the early postpartum period.

Due to the discrepancy between unit data and risk management data reporting, the team who was involved in the new policy implementation should discuss the discrepancies and address the problem. A well-trained reviewer, individual chart reviews for inappropriate cases, and an algorithm to screen elective delivery cases may be needed to ensure that data is accurate for internal and external reporting.

To prevent inappropriate scheduling, such as physicians entering a patient into the unit's schedule book, it is recommended that electronic scheduling be implemented so that only specific staff members, such as the unit's charge nurses, be allowed to schedule. Prompts will also be included so that indications that will allow early elective delivery are prominently displayed and must be present in order for the delivery to be scheduled.

Evaluating the new cash payment package was done to determine the numbers of international patients receiving the recommended evaluation and care by the perinatologist prior to delivery. This policy is anticipated to improve prenatal care for these patients, resulting in healthier infants and fewer NICU admissions. This can also be

evaluated by the number of refusals to pay cases as the parents have received information about the health of the fetus and potential problems the perinatologist anticipated.

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APPENDIX

TABLES OF EVIDENCE

Guidelines For Elective Delivery

Source	Development Process	Findings	Recommendations
<p>To make uniform the definition of the term “pregnancy” and address the lack of uniformity in neonatal outcomes between 37-42 weeks of gestation</p> <p>(ACOG, 2013)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Past definition of term pregnancy is from 3 weeks before and 2 weeks after the estimated gate of delivery • The adverse neonatal outcomes is lowest among 39-40 6/7 gestational age • A work group started in late 2012 to uniform definition of term pregnancy as evidence-based consensus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Neonatal respiratory morbidity vary between 37 weeks to 42 weeks • Between 39-40.6 weeks has lowest adverse neonatal outcomes among uncomplicated pregnancies deliver • Recommended classification Early term : 37-38.6 weeks Full term : 39-40.6 weeks Late term : 41-41.6 weeks Post term : >42 weeks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recommend new gestational age designation • Quality improvement projects to eliminate nonmedical indications for delivery <39 weeks of gestational age
<p>To summarize the efficacy of induction methods</p> <p>(ACOG, 2009)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • >22% pregnant women experience induction in United States • Review most updated approaches for cervical ripening 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nulliparous women should be counseled when undergoing induction of labor because of a doubly increased risk of cesarean section • Cervical ripening will aid in the cervical softening, thinning, and dilating process. • Bishop scoring system can decide cervical status. Bishop score is 6 or less is 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical guidelines for obstetrician and gynecologists • Methods of cervical ripening include prostaglandin E1,2, laminaria, foley catheters (14-26F), misoprostol • Methods of labor induction include pitocin, stripping membrane, ruptured membrane, and stimulation of the nipples

Source	Development Process	Findings	Recommendations
		<p data-bbox="1142 331 1415 386">consider an unfavorable cervix</p> <ul data-bbox="1108 396 1436 716" style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="1108 396 1436 516">• Indications for and contraindications to induction of labor were classified. <li data-bbox="1108 526 1436 716">• Valid indications for induction include risk of rapid labor, distance from hospital, gestational age criteria met, or a mature fetal lung test 	

Ethnicity Issues And Elective Delivery

Purpose	Design/ Sample and Setting	Findings/ Conclusion
To investigate validations for black or South Asian women to deliver <39 weeks of gestational age on planned cesarean sections (Balchin et al., 2008)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prospectively data collection, 585,291 pregnant women from 1988-2000 in North West London • Data collection began first prenatal visit until 28 days after delivery • Data entered by experienced clerks and midwives and using online proof systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • South Asian and black infants deliver after 39 weeks respiratory dysfunction do not improve • For white, term pregnancy elective cesarean section before labor is the major cause of RDS • South Asians have had the lowest chances of TTN before 38 weeks and RDS until 40 weeks
To compare white, black and south Asian duration of pregnancy and its incidence of preterm birth (Balchin& Steer, 2007)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The North West Thames obstetric database • 585,291 births between 1988-2000 • Prospective data collection • 263 maternal, from the first antenatal visit up to 28 days postpartum 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The mean gestation length for black and South Asian was 39 weeks; white 40 weeks • Black and South Asian Infants delivered before 37 weeks have less risk of respiratory distress syndrome with higher survival rate when compared to white infants • Infants delivered 37 weeks and beyond, black infants have higher mortality rate than white infants because of meconium passage and respiratory morbidity • Asian late gestation infants stillbirth occur one week earlier than white infants
To assess primary non-elective cesarean deliveries and implications varied by	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retrospective, cross-sectional cohort five years study 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No significant difference regarding maternal age

Purpose	Design/ Sample and Setting	Findings/ Conclusion
<p>race/ethnicity (Edmonds et al., 2013)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single term pregnant women (37-41 weeks) with vertex presentation included in study • 5 years period, between April 1st, 2006 and March 31st, 2011 • Total of 4,483 low risk women experiencing first pregnancy included in the study • Variables include spontaneous vaginal delivery, operative vaginal delivery and unplanned cesarean delivery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fetal distress was the highest indication for cesarean delivery (40.4%) • White, Black, and Asian women had more than 16% higher rates of cesarean sections than vaginal deliveries • Black women more likely to experience cesarean section for fetal distress compared to white women • A higher rate of primary, unscheduled, intrapartum cesarean delivery among Black and Asian women compared to White

Elective Cesarean Section

Purpose	Design/ Sample and Setting	Findings/ Conclusion
<p>Study relationship between cesarean delivery and maternal request</p> <p>(ACOG, 2013)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systematic literature review • 1,406 articles reviewed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The risk of respiratory morbidity is higher for elective cesarean delivery compared to vaginal delivery when delivery is prior to 39 weeks. (OR 2.6; 95% CI: 1.35-5.9; $p < .01$). • In circumstances where risk indications are absent, a plan for vaginal delivery is recommended • CS on maternal request should not be performed before 39 weeks; should not be encouraged by the inefficiency of adequate pain management; is not recommended for women expecting future pregnancies • The risks of placenta previa, placenta accrete, and gravid hysterectomy increase with each CS
<p>Evaluate the primary elective cesarean delivery on maternal request in the Commonwealth of Virginia, whether hospitals have specific guidelines concerning this practice</p> <p>(Alnaif, Beydoun, 2012)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Descriptive cross-sectional study • 2006, 55 hospitals with 94,938 deliveries in Virginia 31.86% delivered by CS, of which 22.49% were primary CS • Survey by telephone or in-person • 100% response rate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 71.7% hospitals allow on-demand cesarean delivery. • Association between the size of the hospital and the providers' type of characteristics and the practice on demand cesarean delivery was not significant. • All hospital s require gestational age 39 weeks or above to schedule elective cesarean section • Labor and Delivery managers

Purpose	Design/ Sample and Setting	Findings/ Conclusion
		<p>perception on demand elective CS as a patient-driven practice that has little relationship with hospital characteristics</p>
<p>Describe young women with their first pregnancy and their attitudes toward cesarean delivery on maternal demand</p> <p>(Gallagher et al., 2012)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Descriptive study (survey) • Conventional sample included 140 nulliparous women in Canada; 18-24 years of age • 95% native to Canada. 52.9% single;46.4% were married 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Women residing with parents ($p = 0.005$), midwife as favorable caregiver ($p = 0.013$), were less likely to prefer CS • Women who negatively perceived vaginal delivery were more likely to have a CS • CONCLUSION: Inexperienced women are discussing the topic of cesarean delivery on maternal demand and may impact others' decisions towards a more favorable delivery mode
<p>To examine factors that determined physicians response to patient-requested cesarean delivery across a wide range of practice setting</p> <p>(Ghetti et al., 2004)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study conducted in spring 2000 • First study in 18 years to assess physicians' responses to elective CS in United States • Self-administered questionnaire consist 17clinical scenario; 5 questions had medical indications for CS; 5 without indication; 7 with unclear indication for CS • 4 point Likert scale to measure physician willingness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Male physicians significantly agree with perform a CS ($p = .031$) • Male physicians more likely to perform CS for a woman reporting concern for future urinary incontinence or history of stillbirth • For emergency situations, there were no difference between physician genders • When the patient had high socioeconomic status, physicians were more likely to perform CS

Purpose	Design/ Sample and Setting	Findings/ Conclusion
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respondent assume to provide second opinion • A multinomial logistic regression model used • 140 questionnaire for analysis; respondents average age was 47 with average 15 years practice experience 	

Elective Induction and Hospital Policy

Purpose	Design/ Sample and Setting	Findings/ Conclusion
<p>To assess effectiveness of implementing hospital policies on decreasing elective inductions and increasing unplanned rates of labor.</p> <p>(Akinsipe et al., 2012)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systematic Review • Retrospective & prospective • 304 records taken from PubMed, CINAHL, Cochrane Database from 1990-2010 • 9 studies reviewed, assess influence of placing a policy on elective delivery and the results of maternal and neonatal outcomes • 49 primary obstetricians, 8 perinatologists, 40 private practitioners, 8 family practice faculty, 48 family residents involved 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most studies derived from ACOG elective induction policy • 63% women educated about labor induction decided not to have an elective induction • Results of 47,840 laboring women prior to placing policies in place. Post policy implementation samples included 69,519 laboring women • After elective induction policy implementation, maternal morbidity decreased and the rate of neonatal intensive care unit admission decreased. • Practice of elective induction policy resulted in decrease induction, cesarean section and maternal/neonatal morbidity rates.
<p>To investigate whether national elective delivery guideline has changed obstetric practice and has affected perinatal morbidity</p> <p>(Little et al., 2014)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 years retrospective cohort study, between October 1st 2006 to September 30th 2011 • A single tertiary care center • Include singleton, live birth between 37-39.6 weeks gestation • Total of 21343 eligible deliveries • Data collected from hospital's electronic delivery information system and electronic NICU admission log • Gestational age recorded by primary providers by utilizing approximated date of delivery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Between all deliveries of 2006 and 2007, more than 6.5% delivered at 38.6 weeks and more than 8% at greater than 39 weeks • Between all deliveries of 2010 and 2011, more than 4.5% delivered at 38.6 weeks and more than 10% at greater than 39 weeks • NICU admission rate has no changed ($p = .11$)

Elective Delivery Outcomes

Purpose	Design/ Sample and Setting	Findings/ Conclusion
<p>Determining adverse neonatal and maternal outcomes associated with elective delivery at prior to 39 weeks gestational age</p> <p>(Clark et al., 2009)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prospective, observational study • May 1, 2007- July 31, 2007 • Corporation of America system includes 114 hospitals in 21 states • Quality improvement project • Planned term delivery at or beyond 37 weeks • Data collected by a experienced labor and delivery nurses • Web-based data collection • Data analyzed centrally 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 17,794 deliveries, 14,955 (84%) delivered at 37+ weeks. 6562 (44%) term deliveries planned. • Scheduled deliveries: 17.8 % infants delivered electively without medical indication at 37-38 weeks. 8% delivered infants treated in newborn special care unit for 4.5 days, compared to 4.6% of infants delivered 39+ weeks • Cesarean delivery rate in induced women affected by initial cervical dilation and parity • Cervical dilation is highly related to CS • Elective induction women with unfavorable cervix should be counseled regarding an increased rate of CS delivery
<p>To evaluate the risk of neonatal respiratory morbidity delivered at 37-38 weeks compared with those delivered at 39 weeks</p> <p>(Ghartey et al., 2012)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retrospective cohort study from January-December 2010 at New York Presbyterian Children’s Hospital • Multiple gestations and suspected fetal anomalies were excluded • Electronic medical record (maternal demographics, admission diagnoses, indications for delivery, mode of delivery an prior antenatal corticosteroid exposure) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Of 2273 deliveries, 51% delivered in the early term period (37-38 weeks) • Deliveries 37-38 weeks had a doubly increased risk of respiratory distress, oxygen use, continue positive airway pressure use, and composite respiratory morbidity
<p>To approximate elective delivery rate between 36-38.6 wks intra uterine pregnancy (IUP) and examine NICU admission rates between planned and unplanned deliveries.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retrospective cohort study chart reviews to assess correlation between elective delivery prior to 39 weeks and NICU admission 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Via elective vaginal, elective CS and non-elective CS delivery, infants at dramatically increased chance of NICU admission in comparison to infants born

Purpose	Design/ Sample and Setting	Findings/ Conclusion
(Hoffmire et al., 2012)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1577 charts reexamined, final sample size 1521 • The Perinatal Database System at Strong Memorial Hospital used ICD-9 codes, reexamined maternal 36-38.6 weeks admission reasons from, 2006- 2007 	<p>naturally by the onset of labor</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most maternal traits related to elective delivery ($p < .001$) • Consumption of alcohol during pregnancy not related to elective delivery ($p = .410$) • Elective delivery infants were more likely to be SGA or LGA and older than infants born through non-elective delivery ($p < .001$) • Elective delivery prior to 39 weeks increase risk to neonate • Assessing lung maturity between 36-39 weeks before delivery may be neither dependable nor cost effective
<p>To discuss maternal and neonatal complications for maternal request cesarean delivery</p> <p>(Lee & Alton, 2008)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • March 2006, National Institutes of Health-sponsored state-of –the –Science conference on cesarean delivery on maternal request 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Respiratory distress needing mechanical ventilation is decreased to 1/10,000 if elective cesarean delivery >39 weeks • Respiratory morbidity is increased for infants delivered by CS without onset of labor(35.5/1000) compared to cesarean sections (12.2/1000); $p < .0001$ or vaginal delivery (5.3/1000); $p < .0001$) • Steroid administration in the term pregnancy may be beneficial in decreasing respiratory distress. The incidence of admission with respiratory distress was 0.051 in the control group and 0.024 in the treatment group • Infant brachial plexus injury is higher for assisted vaginal deliveries when compared with cesarean

Purpose	Design/ Sample and Setting	Findings/ Conclusion
<p>Review cesarean delivery research and its significance related to risks, economics, ethics, practice, and future research</p> <p>(Miesnik&Reale, 2007)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retrospect literature review 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fever, infection, pneumonia, and thromboembolic consistently increased with cesarean delivery • The risk of placental abruption, placenta previa increases after the first cesarean delivery and with each subsequent cesarean • Cesarean delivery associated with long-term respiratory and autoimmune disorders of infants • Compared to cesarean section newborns, vaginally delivered newborns spend more time with mothers • 40-54% of physicians approve a woman to request cesarean delivery without medical indication • Female physicians are less likely to fulfill maternal requests for cesarean delivery and perform an elective cesarean delivery • Vaginal birth cost 24% lower than cesarean delivery (vaginal birth \$2,487 v.s planned cesarean delivery \$4,372)
<p>Assess associations and infants' outcomes of elective cesarean sections between 37-39 weeks</p> <p>(Tina et al., 2009)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cohort study for repeat CS from 1999-2002 • Of 24,077 repeat CS, 13,258 performed electively • 35.8% performed before 39 weeks; 6.3% at 37 weeks, 29.5% at 38 weeks, 49.1% at 39 weeks • Neonatal outcomes: death, respiratory distress syndrome, transient tachypnea, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 37-38 weeks birth has increased risk of the maternal and infant complications • Elective repeat CS before 39 weeks of gestation is common and is associated with respiratory and other adverse neonatal outcomes

Purpose	Design/ Sample and Setting	Findings/ Conclusion
	<p>hypoglycemia, sepsis, confirmed seizures, necrotizing enterocolitis, hypoxicischemic encephalopathy, cardiopulmonary resuscitation or ventilator support within 24 hours after birth, umbilical cord blood arterial PH below 7.0, a 5 minutes Apgar score of 3 or below, admission to NIU, and prolonged hospitalization(5 days or longer) were studied</p>	
<p>To assess the number and timing of elective cesarean sections at term and to evaluate the perinatal outcome correlated to this timing.</p> <p>(Wilmink & Hukkelhoven, 2010)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retrospective cohort analysis • 20,973 single pregnancy at term • Calculation of gestation age was determined by first-trimester ultrasound 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 50% of neonates born at < 39 wks.; dramatically higher risk than neonate born after • The absolute risks were 20.6% at 37-37.6wks. 12.55% at 38-38.6wks, 9.5% at 39-39.6wks of gestation • Most neonatal health results show dramatic trends ($P < .05$) toward an increased incidence for delivery <39 weeks.

Financial Impact

Purpose	Design/ Sample and Setting	Findings/ Conclusion
<p>To provide an overview of economic issues surrounding elective cesarean section</p> <p>(Petrou& Khan, 2013)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Literature review • 15 studies with 12 relevant reporting include health economic evaluation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planned CS may cost less than planned NSVD (Can \$7,165 vs. \$8,042) • For low risk cases, CS cost more than NSVD • The mean cost of the hospital stay following elective CS between 1.1-4.1 times vs. following NSVD • Trial of labor following previous CS is more cost-effective than elective CS

Notes. ACOG = American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists. CS = Cesarean section. DV = Dependent variable. IV = Independent variable. IUP= Intrauterine pregnancy. LGA = large for gestational age. NSVD = Normal spontaneous vaginal delivery. NICU = neonatal intensive care. RDS = Respiratory distress syndrome. SGA = Small for gestational age. TTN = Transient tachypnea of the newborn. VBAC = Vaginal birth after cesarean section.

